

The Viva Voce; the last dance or last chance?

Carol Kennedy-Gardiner

carol.kennedygardiner64@mail.dcu.ie

This paper delineates the preparation process for the final defence of a doctoral thesis that emphasised the perceptions and experiences of learners deemed to have Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD) through a critical disability lens. This research focused on post-primary education in Ireland, aiming to identify and improve inclusive educational strategies for learners. This paper compares the preparation for a Viva Voce for this study to wedding planning, highlighting the significance of meticulous and strategic organisation in both contexts. The article illustrates how candidates can effectively plan their defence by using each aspect of the thesis, including research questions, conceptual framework, methodology, findings, and discussion. This paper aligns these techniques with personal experiences, providing a practical resource for PhD candidates to traverse the Viva Voce process with confidence. The paper concludes by highlighting the significance of thorough preparation for the Viva Voce, which includes reviewing research contributions, practicing summarisation, and participating in mock vivas. The analogy of a wedding exemplifies the complex preparation required for both events, ensuring that the researcher is prepared to defend their work and engage in the wider discussion on inclusive education for learners deemed to have DCD.

Key Words: Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD), Critical Disability Perspective, Inclusive Education, Viva Voce Preparation

Highlights

- The paper draws a unique comparison between preparing for a Viva Voce and planning a wedding, illustrating the importance of strategic organisation, meticulous preparation, and reflection in both contexts to ensure success.
- The paper highlights what key topics and issues were reviewed in advance on the Viva Voce, in particular its key outcomes regarding the need for systemic changes in school culture and policies.
- The Viva is depicted as a significant milestone in the Doctoral journey, akin to a wedding, requiring thorough preparation and serving as a platform for advocacy and academic engagement. A "checklist" methodology for Viva preparation parallels wedding planning responsibilities, highlighting systematic preparation to guarantee readiness and success.

This paper outlines the journey of preparing for the final defence of a doctoral thesis, focusing on a study that investigates the perceptions and experiences of learners deemed to have Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD) from a critical disability perspective. The research, targeting post-primary school learners in the Republic of Ireland, sought to identify supportive strategies within an inclusive educational framework. This paper provides an overview of the process of preparing for a final thesis defence (Viva Voce) for this study. The purpose of this paper is to identify supportive techniques that can benefit all doctoral candidates. Using the analogy of a wedding, the paper compares the preparation for a Viva Voce to wedding planning. In many ways, preparing for the Viva Voce mirrors the anticipation and planning involved in a wedding. This comparison is used to describe the various stages and elements involved in preparing for a Viva Voce. The aim of this paper is to provide supportive techniques and guidance for all doctoral candidates as they engage in the final stages of their doctoral journey.

Context and Background

The Viva Voce is an oral examination in which the doctoral student presents and defends their thesis before internal examiners from their institution and external examiners from another university who specialize in their subject area (Roffey-Barentsen & Malthouse, 2020; Tan, 2023). Much like a wedding day represents a significant milestone in a marriage, the Viva Voce holds comparable importance in the life of a doctoral candidate. Instead of buying a dress, losing weight, and aiming to look their best, the researcher prepares by thoroughly reviewing their work, drinking copious amounts of coffee to stay alert, possibly gaining weight, and sometimes appearing a bit dishevelled! During the Viva, the researcher's supervisor may attend as a passive observer (King, Gravina & Sleiman, 2018), much like the witnesses at a wedding who offer support and ensure everything goes smoothly.

The possible outcomes of a Viva Voce examination can be categorized into three results: passing without required changes, passing with minor or major revisions, or failing (Potter, 2006; Duke, 2020; van Teijlingen et al., 2022). In the context of marriage, these outcomes have parallels. The first outcome resembles a "pass without corrections," symbolizing smooth sailing and lasting happiness. The second outcome, "passing with minor or major corrections," mirrors the recognition that marriage requires work and has ups and downs. The third outcome, "not passing at all," is akin to a marriage that doesn't succeed (Duke, 2020; van Teijlingen et al.,

2022). According to Delamont et al. (2004), outright failure is rare but not impossible. Marriage, like earning a doctorate, demands commitment, perseverance, and resilience.

The author's own experiences of doctoral research will be used as a lens in which to examine preparation for the Viva Voce process. While significant research has focused on Special Educational Needs (SEN), there is a noticeable lack of attention to learners with Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD), especially in Ireland (O'Dea, Coote & Robinson, 2019; O'Dea, 2021). The author's doctoral research addresses this gap by exploring strategies that schools can employ to better support these students. The study adopts an inclusive and critical disability perspective, moving away from a deficit-based view of DCD. This paper delves into the post-research phase associated with this study, involving the preparation for the final defence of the completed, written, and submitted work using each of the broad areas of a thesis document (research questions, conceptual framework, methodology, findings, discussion) as a guide for Viva Voce preparation.

Research Questions

Research questions play a critical role in the Viva Voce, serving as the foundation for the defence (Mežek & Swales, 2016; Mayengo, 2020). Similar to fundamental marriage principles, these questions guide the discussion and activities of the Viva Voce (Roffey-Barentsen & Malthouse, 2020). The research question serves as a compass, providing direction and focus for the study (Hall & Wall, 2019). Research questions help maintain focus during the research process (Berman, 2013), which is essential during the Viva Voce as it organizes the conversation around key topics (Nind, Curtin & Hall, 2016). Furthermore, it shows the examiners that the student remained aligned with the primary research objectives throughout the study (Berman, 2013).

The research questions also help both the student and examiner assess the study topic's understanding (Posselt, 2018). Discussing the questions demonstrates the student's in-depth knowledge of the topic (Hall & Wall, 2019). During the Viva, this discussion helps examiners evaluate how well the student grasps the essential concepts and theories related to their research (Mudzielwana, 2016). Consequently, well-formulated research questions provide a structure for organising the doctoral dissertation (Duke, 2020). They are integrated into the conceptual framework, serving as a key component that helps both doctoral students and examiners

navigate the research (Berman, 2013). A clear structure is vital for delivering a cohesive argument during the Viva (Hickman & Palmer, 2011).

During a Viva Voce, the student must justify their choice of specific research questions (Roffey-Barentsen & Malthouse, 2020), explaining their importance and relevance. This shows that the student has identified gaps in the literature (Mudzielwana, 2016) and that their research aims to address these gaps in the findings and discussion sections (Crossouard, 2011). This reasoning is crucial in demonstrating the work's significance and originality (Cryer, 2006). The study must focus on a specific area insufficiently covered in the existing literature (Potter, 2006). Research questions often stem from a thorough literature review (Davis & Engward, 2018; Merrins, 2022; Tan, 2023). Discussing these questions in the Viva demonstrates that the student has rigorously examined the literature, establishing their work's relevance within the broader academic context (Delamont, Atkinson & Parry, 2004). This discussion is essential for highlighting the research's impact and significance (Hartley & Fox, 2004). Furthermore, research questions are closely tied to the study's methods (Duke, 2020). Discussing them enables the doctoral student to explain and defend the methods used to address these questions, showcasing their methodological rigor and analytical skills (Wellington, 2010). This part of the Viva is critical, as it displays the student's expertise in conducting rigorous research (Paul & Marfo, 2001).

Developing and answering research questions requires critical reasoning and analytical skills (Mayengo, 2020; van Teijlingen et al., 2022). Through these questions, the student shows their ability to thoughtfully analyse the research issue and offer new insights to the field (Duke, 2020). This demonstration of critical thinking is fundamental in the Viva (Merrins, 2022). The doctoral thesis should not only address a gap in the existing literature but also tackle a distinct challenge within the educational system (Tan, 2023). The professional life of a doctoral student is vital in making a meaningful contribution by combining their professional skills with research expertise (Bell & Waters, 2018; Merrins, 2022). By discussing their research questions, the doctoral student highlights the unique and innovative aspects of their study and its contribution to knowledge advancement in their field (Duke, 2020). This judgment is essential for illustrating the research's importance (King, Gravina & Sleiman, 2018).

In a Viva Voce, referring back to research questions in all discussions is a useful approach as they encapsulate the essence of the study, guiding the conversation and enabling the student to showcase the depth and breadth of their academic work.

Central Concept

To successfully defend key research issues during an oral examination, the researcher must have full confidence in the foundation of their work (Paul & Marfo, 2001; Zina, 2021). A strong marriage is built on mutual respect, effective communication, trust, shared values, and a commitment to personal growth and compromise, much like a robust scientific investigation is grounded in core principles and rigorous methodology (Bell & Waters, 2018).

The author's research adopted a critical disability perspective, aligning with the global shift away from the traditional medical approach to disability and towards recognising biases in Special Educational Needs (SEN) (McCauley, 2020). This perspective examines the power dynamics, inequalities, and societal changes required to achieve an all-encompassing educational experience for Irish adolescents with Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD) upon completing primary education. Employing a critical disability perspective provides a coherent framework for understanding the research, benefiting the researcher, supervisors, and examiners (Meekosha & Shuttleworth, 2009; Goodley, 2013; Vehmas & Watson, 2014; Ellis et al., 2019; Shildrick, 2019). It is crucial that examiners and doctoral candidates have a shared understanding of these concepts (Bell & Waters, 2018; Duke, 2020; Zina, 2021) so regular reference to the conceptual framework that was contained within the submitted written work was done in the Viva Voce.

To frame the researcher's thinking and guide the process within the Viva Voce, the conceptual framework was vital. Within the thesis document, the conceptual framework resembled a map that began as a rudimentary overview and grew more detailed as the researcher became familiar with the terrain. A study's conceptual framework should incorporate realistic and measurable outcomes (Kivunja, 2018), with the overarching objective of keeping the researcher focused throughout the process (Leshem and Trafford, 2007). It significantly influenced the research's emerging themes and issues (Leshem & Trafford, 2007; Berman, 2013) but also acted as a touchstone for the student to refer to when justifying different decisions within the Viva Voce.

Methodology

The research methodology significantly influences the Viva Voce by helping the audience understand the connections between the research topics and questions (Kumar, 2018).

Examiners can perceive the dynamics between main elements and their interactions (Potter, 2006; Duke, 2020; Roffey-Barentsen & Malthouse, 2020).

The author's work that was examined at Viva Voce in 2024 rigorously examined qualitative data generated from learners diagnosed with DCD who are currently attending or have recently completed mainstream post-primary education in Ireland. The data were gathered through thirteen individual semi-structured interviews and three focus groups, with each focus group comprising three participants (Flick, 2004; Braun & Clarke, 2021; Maxwell, 2021; Leotti, Sugrue & Wings-Yanez, 2022). Data analysis employed Thematic Analysis, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022), and was informed by the interpretive framework of Critical Disability Studies (CDS). In preparing for discussions on the study's methodology, the author effectively planned their defence by using each aspect of the thesis, including research questions, conceptual framework, methodology, findings, and discussion.

Findings and Discussion

Research is characterised by its findings and analysis (Crossouard, 2011; Hickman & Palmer, 2011; Davis & Engward, 2018), which represent its essence, much like the dynamic connection between a bride and groom at a wedding. The core passion and vitality of the research lie in these discoveries and analyses, akin to the early affection that garners extensive attention and conversation (Zina, 2021). The researcher must be able to effectively communicate their findings and their implications (Delamont, Atkinson & Parry, 2004; Mežek & Swales, 2016; Roffey-Barentsen & Malthouse, 2020). This is a key element of the Viva Voce process and rests on a thorough understanding of the relevance of the key findings as well as comfort in orally communicating such information.

Many Critical Disability Studies (CDS) researchers argue that power is deeply intertwined with social interactions (Fairclough, 2010), with individuals socially categorised as either competent or impaired in specific contexts (Kilinc, 2021; Symeonidou, 2022). This research highlighted a pressing need to reassess current structures, practices, and policies supporting learners deemed to have DCD in Irish secondary schools. Key areas of concern emerged during the author's data analysis, underscoring the importance of creating inclusive, trauma-sensitive school cultures, policies, and practices. Evidence suggests that inclusive, responsive, equitable, and humanising learning environments are essential for learners deemed to have DCD. In preparing for the Viva Voce, the author extensively practices and refined their oral communication of these points in anticipation for the examiner's questions.

Given that the area of the researcher's work was within inclusive education, the Viva discussion was likely to centre on the amplification of learners' voices in the research, advocating for substantial changes in culture, policy, and practice. This advocacy is supported by Prunty, Dupont, and McDaid (2012), Edmonds (2013), and Davies and Ryan (2014). Discussions on culture should focus on influencing those responsible for setting inclusivity agendas at both national and school levels. This will ensure a clear and inclusive message that promotes a sense of belonging within the school environment (McMaster & Elliot, 2014; Morrissey, 2020). At the policy level, a comprehensive vision of inclusion requires national legislative changes and updated school policies (Brown et al., 2020; Skerritt, 2020; Skerritt, Brown & O'Hara, 2023). Teachers need to use innovative differentiation and inclusion strategies, making small adjustments to their daily routines to better support learners (Lindner & Schwab, 2020). By proactively considering both the theoretical and practical implications of the research findings, the author successfully positioned the study within the wider discourse of Critical Disability Studies and inclusive education. This highlighted the work's contribution to academia. Contemplating these factors before the Viva Voce enabled the author to be thoroughly equipped to defend the study, assert its importance, and participate in substantive academic discourse. This preparation guaranteed that the author presented a persuasive argument on the significance and influence of the study.

Preparing for the Viva: A Countdown

Preparing for the Viva is like preparing for a wedding: it requires organisation, anticipation, and practice. When preparing for my wedding, the author undertook tasks like drafting a checklist, holding a rehearsal, printing booklets, arranging the cake, welcoming relatives, and coordinating with the venue. A rigorous checklist ensured everything went smoothly. Similarly, preparing for the Viva Voce requires meticulous planning to ensure a successful outcome (Potter, 2006; Duke, 2020; Zina, 2021). This includes a mock Viva, printing the thesis, preparing questions, and coordinating with supervisors (Merrins, 2022). Three key elements that should be on any Viva Voce checklist include:

- **Practice Summarising the Thesis:** Prepare concise summaries of each chapter, along with a two-minute overview of the entire thesis (Merrins, 2022). Participating in university-organised events like DCU's 'Unconference' and 'Research on the Walls' can aid in this preparation (Wellington, 2010; Watts, 2012).

- **Anticipate General Questions:** Develop responses for both broad and specific questions (Merrins, 2022), akin to answering difficult questions expected from a wedding officiant.
- **Conduct Mock Vivas:** Engage in a mock Viva with a supervisor to gain confidence and receive constructive feedback (Hartley & Fox, 2004).
- **Oral Communication:** In the final 24-48 hours, review prepared responses to ensure full readiness for the day (Merrins, 2022). Speaking responses aloud will enhance their authenticity on the Viva Voce day, just as on one's wedding day.

Post-Viva: Continuing the Journey

Just as a marriage continues beyond the wedding, the journey continues after the Viva Voce, with tasks such as editing, submitting, publishing, and engaging in ongoing discussions. This should be borne in mind, particularly if certain deadlines must be met for graduation etc. This journey is marked by both major milestones celebrated with friends and family and long hours of dedicated work.

Conclusion

This paper outlines the process of preparing for a doctoral Viva Voce, centring on research that investigated the perceptions and experiences of learners deemed to have Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD) through a critical disability lens. The study aimed to foster more inclusive educational practices within Irish post-primary schools. The Viva Voce is highlighted as a significant milestone, comparable to a wedding, requiring careful planning, reflection, and strategic preparation. Understanding the research questions is essential, as they guide the study and form the foundation of the defence. The Viva Voce highlighted the necessity of illustrating how the research methodology, based on qualitative data and thematic analysis within a Critical Disability Studies framework, effectively linked research questions, conceptual framework, findings, and discussion to demonstrate the study's coherence and rigour. The findings of the author's research emphasised the need for inclusive strategies for learners deemed to have DCD. While this was discussed in written form in the thesis, the Viva Voce for those within the field of inclusive education serves as an advocacy platform for essential changes in culture, policy, and practice that would support future learners. The Viva often concentrates on the researcher's capacity to justify their work, especially concerning its methodology, findings, and conclusions. The author's anticipation of questions on the practical and theoretical implications of the work prepared them to respond convincingly, demonstrating a profound understanding and thought process. Anticipating these elements prior to the Viva Voce allowed the author to

be well prepared to defend their research, emphasise its significance, and engage in meaningful intellectual dialogue. This preparation ensured they delivered a compelling argument regarding the importance and impact of the findings.

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